

THE ARCHITECT AND UNIQUENESS OF THE ISHRATKHANA MAUSOLEUM

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Abstract: In this article, among the works aimed at increasing the tourism potential of Uzbekistan, the role of the ancient shrines in the historical and cultural regions of our Republic, especially the architecture of the Sufism places of the past, is incomparable. Including, the monument of the Ishratkhana complex gives an understanding of the importance of the reconstruction, restoration and conservation of increasing the potential for tourism. Weather conditions in Obi, a new view of the landscape, and the development of monuments and tourist sites show their importance in increasing the tourism potential.

Keywords: Dilkusho, Mionsaroy, Palace, flower garden, protection, monument, porch, porch.

Today, the process of reconstruction and restoration of historical monuments is of urgent importance in the preservation of cultural heritage in our country. "On the protection and use of objects of the cultural heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and "On the implementation of the law on the protection and use of the objects of archaeological heritage" dated 13.10.2009, on the legal relations regarding the protection of the objects ensuring control over compliance with other regulatory laws. In order to preserve the irreplaceable characteristics of the object of material cultural heritage and its historical environment, protection zones, zones for regulating the construction of buildings and economic activities, protected natural landscape zones are defined in the area adjacent to it. Since the first years of our independence, preservation, repair and protection of historical and cultural heritage objects has been raised to the level of state policy. Because "objects of cultural heritage are the nation's priceless wealth, it is our duty to preserve them and pass them on to future generations". [1]

In the history of the city of Samarkand, the condition of the medieval period has been preserved. The artistry of the city had its own basis. Among the mass, simple structures, there were many magnificent blue (lajvard) Temur and the remains of buildings from the Timurid era.

Ishratkhona complex Architectural monument in Samarkand. It tells the story of Amir Temur's romantic meeting with a girl, after which the palace building in the middle of Dilkusho garden, built during the reign of the great Amir Temur (1397-98). The architectural forms and elegant decorations of the Ishratkhana are luxurious, the beautiful building in the middle of the garden surrounded by a high wall is like Dilkusho (30x22.4 m) gable, with two-story rooms adjacent to the two wings. The structure is made of stone, the decoration is made of smooth brick, the seams are covered with turquoise and blue tiles. There is another small arch inside the arch of Peshtok, and there is an inscription on its inner wall. It is entered through two

small doors and a gate. A large room with a height of two floors is exited through a lattice door of the miyansarai (size 8x8 m). It leads to a 3-room mansion. Pants. and moved to a long room with an altar (presumably, a mosque). There are 4 circular staircases in the outer corners of the Mion Palace, through which access to the upper attic rooms (rooms) and the dome roof. The palace property and foodstuffs were stored in the eight-sided underground "cistern"-cellar under the Mion Palace. The basement is made of tiles and stone.

Ishratkhana Architectural monument in Samarkand (XV century). According to another assumption, the name of the monument comes from Arabic asharat, which means ten (ten rooms).

Ishratkhana - translated from Persian, "Ishratkhana" means "House of Entertainment".

The Ishratkhana complex was mentioned for the first time in the historical brochure "Samaria" of the 1930s. It shows that the Ishratkhana was founded by Khabib Sultan, the daughter of Amir Jalaluddin. In the middle of the 19th century, topographer Yakovlev, a member of the Russian embassy in Bukhara, was planning the city of Samarkand. Academician V. Bartold, in his study of Samarkand, gave the name of the khan's Ishratkhana, which was turned into a promenade palace, as a "Nestorian monument". The dictionary meaning of the Ishratkhana is interpreted in two ways.

The ceiling of the Mion Palace is made up of very complex intersecting arches and shield-shaped arches in the corners. The pattern is a tile pattern, the top of it is white, and it has become a pattern of colorful flowers on the ganch. Among them, the kundal flowers, slightly protruding, brightened the room. The top of the palace is covered with a second dome from the outside. This dome is tall and majestic because it is placed on a high circular girdle. The surface of the belt is decorated with grooved tile patterns. The dome is completely covered with turquoise bricks. That is why the dome was later called "blue dome". Islamic and Giri motifs, gilded kundal decorations in the office are among the unique masterpieces of the national architectural treasure. Even

now, the remains of Ishrat Khana, though much has been lost, look beautiful and attractive. Its high dome was built in 1903. collapsed during a strong earthquake.

Ishratkhana Amir Temur's building occupies a special place in the history of Uzbekistan's architecture as the most famous and the most magnificent of the garden palaces built around Samarkand with special dedication and under his personal supervision. In the Ishratkhana, the first archaeological works were carried out in 1939-1940 by academicians M.E. Masson and G.A. Pugachenkova, as a result of which it was found that the mausoleum was located on a large foundation, which was deepened by almost 5 meters. The office was a unique building of the 15th century. Prominent personalities and master craftsmen of that time worked in the construction of the palace. At that time, a special revolution took place in the architecture of Samarkand. Many researchers praised the art of its creators and noted not only the infinite luxury of the design of this building - a mausoleum or a palace, but also that radically new architectural techniques and solutions were involved in its construction. The Ishratkhana complex includes the following: a mosque with a beautiful and modest interior, several rooms on the 1st and 2nd floors where funeral rites are held using the "kundal" technique, and funeral prayers. In the 16th century, the mausoleum fell into disrepair. More precisely, it was robbed. This was caused by the intense construction work that began in Samarkand in the 17th century. At first, the office was separated from the marble panel. Because large plates were needed for the Sher-Dor and Tillakori madrasas built in Registan. Also, the marble tombstones were taken to the neighboring

Beijing Dome was built in 1872. can be determined from the photo taken at.

Abdi-Darun cemetery, and new marble stones were placed instead of the old ones.

The only source for the Ishratkhana complex

Information about the single foundation document related to the monument is stored in the document fund of the Samarkand State Museum-Reserve. According to him, this foundation document was written at the beginning of the month of Ramadan 868 AH (May 1463), and among other seals, the seal of Abu Said ibn Sultan Muhammad ibn Mironshah ibn Amir Temur, the ruler of Khurasan, was printed on the document. In the document, the name of the mausoleum is called the mausoleum of Sultan Khovand Beka, and it is indicated that it was built by Habiba Sultan Begim, the daughter of Amir Jalaluddin Sukhrob, near the mausoleum of Khwaja Abdu Darun in the western corner of Feruza Park. It is noted that half of the lands of Malik Sarayi village, located on the way from Samarkand to Shahrisabz, were donated to the mausoleum. This foundation document was approved by the Qazi of Samarkand in the month of Shaaban 870 Hijri (March-April 1466).[7]

Creation history Ishratkhana complex is located on the southeast side of the square, on the outskirts of the old city. In the years of Amir Temur's rule, a road leading from "Darvozai Feruza" to "Boghi Dilkusho" and "Boghi Boldi" passed from here. According to Abu Tahirkhoja's work "Samaria", this building was built for his daughter Sultan Havand Beka by the order of Habiba Sultan Beg, the wife of Abu Said Mirza, one of the Timurid rulers. The Ishratkhana complex was built in a short time, i.e. in 3-4 years.

Construction work was completed in May 1463. Originally built for Khawand Sultan, this luxurious mausoleum later became a family hut for the women and children of the Timurid dynasty. As a result of the archaeological excavations, the dahma with 20 graves found here differs from the saganas known in Central Asia by its grandeur and size. The Ishratkhana complex, like Amir Temur's mausoleum, consists of a different room and a shrine. However, this mausoleum differs from other monuments of the Timurid period in that there is a second floor under its dome. The mausoleum of the mausoleum, like the mausoleum of Amir Temur, has 8-9 diameters, is octagonal, and has a well-preserved roof. The graves in the Khilkhana were not preserved, even if they were preserved, they may have been buried under piles of soil that fell into the Khilkhana in different years. The first floor of the mausoleum has one additional room on both sides. A staircase leading down to the hall was built through the room on the south-western side. There are stairs leading to the second floor of the mausoleum through rooms on both sides. The total number of stairs is 4. There are also rooms on both sides of the mausoleum entrance.[2]

What is the purpose of the second floor of the complex? The mausoleum also has a second floor, which is not found in other mausoleums built during the Timurid period and later. In this respect, it always attracts the attention of researchers and tourists. According to the mentioned foundation document, on the second floor there was a Qur'an reciter for those buried in the mausoleum (referred to as a hafiz in the foundation document), a supervisor and a servant. Qori was paid 364 fulus and 192 pounds of grain, the supervisor was paid 404 fulus and 160 pounds of grain, and the servant was paid 204 fulus and 192 pounds of grain. These funds were covered by the income from the lands of Malik Saray village allocated for the mausoleum. On the roof of the second floor there was a tall dome that has not reached us. According to V. Vyatkin, who headed the Samarkand Museum, the dome of the mausoleum was 26.7 meters above the ground and 7.8 meters above the roof of the second floor. The diameter of the dome drum was 8.75 meters, not too big. Unlike other buildings of the Timurid period, the walls are made of 2 bricks thick. Taking into

account that the mausoleum was dedicated to Sultan Khovand Bika, and later women and children belonging to the Timurid family were buried in the mausoleum, it is appropriate to call it "Timurilar mausoleum" or "Sultan Khovand Bika" mausoleum, not "Ashratkhana".

Archaeological tourism resources are valuable and unique. Because they were created by the people of the ancient times and preserved the atmosphere of that time. These objects have become more valuable over time and will continue to do so. The most important factor in this regard is not to damage the archaeological monuments, because any damage cannot be restored. Therefore, tourism resources should be used only by presenting them in a different form. As for such features, we need to pay special attention to conservation and sustainable development when we try to turn archaeological resources into tourism products. With its ancient history, our country attracts the attention of the whole world, Khiva, Bukhara, Shahrissabz, which have been included in the UNESCO World Heritage List, Tashkent, which has been important in Central Asia since ancient times, and many other cities are tourists. is attracting attention. Many amenities are created for tourists in these cities, and during the trip, they feel as if they have entered the ancient times. Archaeological tourism is a bridge between the past and the present. Its principles are completely scientific, and it strives to optimally use archaeological tourist sites as a huge source of tourism. In order to attract tourists, it is necessary to create and reconstruct heritage objects, present attractions in a complex way, and turn archaeological monuments into tourism products. Through this system, while benefiting the state economy, it is possible to study the history and scientifically study new objects, and at the same time, it is possible to see enough income for digging new objects.[5]

It is known that all preserved architectural monuments are worn out over time due to the natural climatic environment and external influences, and the process of weathering and deformation takes place in them. The task of preserving them requires repair work to be carried out by specialists using scientifically based methods. Because it is clear that the repair of the monument will be of poor quality if the reasons for the

destruction of the monument are not determined and not based on scientific and theoretical grounds. Monitoring the deformation of the building in time shows the correct way of strengthening the constructions of the monument in the future.

Even now, the remains of the Ishratkhana, although they have lost a lot of parts, look beautiful and attractive. Its high dome collapsed during a strong earthquake in 1903. The structure of the Peking Dome can be identified from a photograph taken in 1872. Office. Amir Temur's building occupies a special place in the history of Uzbekistan's architecture as the most famous and the most magnificent of the garden palaces built around Samarkand with special devotion and under his personal supervision, especially as the only example that has survived.

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